

Academic Identities in Today's University: A Visual Study.

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Abstract: Recent years have seen the development of accountability processes to monitor the quality, autonomy, and performance of universities. These include the evaluation of university academics based on a quality quantification system that prioritizes research over other roles. For Spanish academics, their professional trajectories hinge entirely on successfully navigating evaluation procedures of this type. This study analyses the impact of these processes on the academic identity of university teaching staff through an alternative and complementary perspective using visual methodologies. To this end, we employed collaborative image creation processes and engaged in reflective analysis, applying both narrative (vertical) and paradigmatic (horizontal) approaches. The results reveal the particular impact of evaluation processes on the identity of university academics. Additionally, we observed the influence of other elements that further amplify this impact, including job insecurity, the quest for employment stability, autonomy to fulfill the work role, as well as the prevalence of inequalities and competitiveness within access procedures. Consequently, we have identified the development of identities with distinct nuances, all underpinned by a common thread: subservience to the demands of evaluation processes, which have emotional and health consequences. This article concludes by proposing lines of action to enable the optimal development of academics.

Keywords: accountability; academics identity; visual methodology; higher education.

Introduction

The development of policies aimed at improving the quality of Higher Education has led to several changes that are altering the structure and the social purposes and functions of universities (Javadi and Azizzadeh,2020). These changes include the proliferation of accountability processes based on an evaluation to monitor quality, autonomy, and performance of universities (Macheridis and Paulsson,2021). Such evaluations aim to assess the development and functioning of elements including curricula and mobility, institutions and centers, and degrees and teaching. Here, we will focus on those evaluations aimed at assessing the quality of university faculty.

In this respect, it should be noted that the evaluation of academics is based on a system for quantifying quality, which gives priority to research over their other functions (teaching, management, internationalization, etc.). Furthermore, the criteria established to resolve processes related to access, promotion, obtaining salary complements (payments added to the base salary) and funding place research as a reference point for professional stabilization and promotion, which means that academics may be conditioned to concentrate their efforts on research. In this sense, and as Saura and Bolívar (2019) point out, evaluation significantly impacts the professional development of academics.

The identity of university faculty is not only determined by trends in evaluation systems but is also influenced by aspects such as departmental/institutional culture, interpersonal relationships, multitasking demands, the progressive internationalization of academic activity, changes in the profile of incoming students, and the increasing bureaucratization of working conditions (job insecurity, short-term contracts, increased competitiveness, salary dissatisfaction), among others (Acker and Webber,2017; Aprile

et al.,2021; Mantai,2019). All of these elements significantly impact the professional development of university faculty. In this regard, recent years have seen a growing scientific concern about the consequences that these neoliberal processes driving performativity, self-governance, and accountability could have for university faculty (Mula-Falcón and Caballero,2022). Studies in this line focus on determining this influence on professional activity and ethics, professional and social relations, and health, as well as the development of academic identity (Cannizzo,2017; Shams,2019, Ursin et al.,2020).

In this regard, it is also worth noting that previous review studies (Mula-Falcón et al.,2021) have found that most research focused on analyzing the academic identity of university faculty employs a qualitative approach through the use of interviews, observations, and focus groups, thus adhering to the traditional practice most commonly used in research on higher education and identity (Kie and Harland,2018).

This work adds to the existing qualitative research focused on studying the academic identity of university faculty. However, in this case, we provide a complementary and innovative approach by applying a visual method. This methodology allows us to break with "the power dynamics inherent in traditional research methods, in which the researcher usually makes the key decisions that pertain to the research process" (Sutton-Brown, 2014, p. 171).

The main underlying objective of this study is to analyze today's university faculties' academic identity through participatory visual methodologies. To this end, the aim to *analyze the academic identity of today's university faculty*, exploring the factors that have an impact on this identity and the consequences that they generate. For this, we will first describe the academic identity approach used in this study and the broader

social context surrounding the current higher education system. Next, the methodological principles employed are presented, the research process is described, and the main results are shown. Finally, we conclude with a discussion of the results in relation to the previous literature.

Academic identity in today's universities

Identity is a complex concept due to its eminently subjective nature. Although this concept has traditionally been approached from different perspectives, we adopted an interactionist perspective for the purposes of this study. Thus, we understand academic identity or "sense of academic self" as a subjective and social construction and reconstruction resulting from the interaction of one's self-image with elements such as personal beliefs, motivations, and values; lived experiences; and the characteristics of the broader social context (e.g., political, economic, social, cultural) (Lankveld et al.,2017). In this regard, scholars such as Clarke et al. (2013) and Kreber (2010) emphasize heterogeneity and diversity as fundamental characteristics of academic identity. Even when confronted with similar situations, individuals show distinct ways of understanding and coping.

Moreover, independent of this interactionist perspective, the literature points to the special impact of contextual factors on the processes of identity construction and development (Alonso et al.,2015; Lankveld et al.,2017). In this regard, factors such as the characteristics of the immediate working environment (professional relationships and working conditions) and the features of the wider system in which they perform their roles (currently characterized by the prominence of professional performance assessment processes, the outcomes of which determine access, advancement, or obtaining incentives in the profession), are emerging as key elements.

This set of elements produce internal identity conflicts far away from the traditional debate between teaching-researcher roles (Zabalza, 2009). On the contrary, the conflicts are generated within each individual as a result of the clash between their own self-perception and the manner in which they conduct their professional activity (Shams, 2019). Consequently, we have witnessed the emergence of polyhedral identities characterized by diverse perspectives on the state of the university system (ranging from positive or negative to neutral), different attitudes towards the system (resistance, rejection, or acceptance), and the cultivation of different values and practices (including traditional or performative), among other aspects (Mula-Falcón et al.,2021).

However, and despite the heterogeneity mentioned above, the international literature has consistently emphasized the notable impact of these contextual factors in the formation of identities characterized by an acceptance of the new performative demands of the contemporary university (Aprile et al.,2021; Djerasimovic and Villani,2019).

This shift has given rise to identities primarily centered on the development of practices aimed at promoting scientific productivity, often at the cost of an individual's wellbeing and family life (Huang and Guo,2019; Ursin et al.,2020). Various authors have argued that this prevailing trend stems from the need to avoid possible professional rejection and/or the pursuit of job security (Cannizzo,2017; San Fabián,2020).

Accountability and the Spanish case

The presence of quality assurance strategies in higher education policy agendas has become increasingly explicit, so accountability processes have been spreading across countries globally, permeating and focusing on different aspects, and materializing through different mechanisms (Jongbloed et al.,2018).

In this regard, university faculty evaluations play a fundamental role due to their

influential nature, as they can generate changes in academics' ways of doing and proceeding (Saura and Bolívar,2019). These evaluations are characterized by the priority given to research activity over the other roles of university faculty. Thus, scientific production has become the main requirement for entry, permanence, and promotion in the university context (Fernández-Cano,2021). Moreover, these processes that drive the so-called 'self-accountability' concept have spread globally (Browning et al.,2017), including Spain.

In Spain, access, career advancement and/or job security within the university profession are contingent upon a dual evaluation process that is repeated for each of the four existing professional categories (assistant doctor, contracted doctor, university professor, and full university professor). This process consists of two components: the first step involves obtaining national accreditation, followed by the second requirement of passing an examination administered by the universities themselves.

The national accreditation process is overseen by the national agency for the evaluation of the quality of the university system (ANECA, in its Spanish acronym). This institution evaluates the merits of teaching staff in terms of the criteria established by the law (RD 415/2015), which include teaching, research, management, knowledge transfer and professional experience outside the university environment. However, these evaluations assign a greater weight to research activity, with a particular emphasis on scientific production in high impact journals. For instance, in the assistant and contracted doctor categories, research accounts for 60% of the total evaluation, while in the professor and full professor categories it is described as a priority merit over the rest of the functions without specifying percentages.

Once accreditation has been obtained, public competitions, organized by the universities

themselves, are held for both hiring assistant doctors and promoting faculty members (contracted doctor, professor, and full professor). For assistant doctors, these tests focus on the presentation of qualifications. In these tests, as in the case of accreditations, research output carries the greatest weight, accounting for between 55% and 45 % of the assessment criteria. Concerning the other categories, the competition entails a public presentation to evaluate the academic, teaching, and research record along with a teaching and research project aligned with the requirements of the position. These tests do not give priority to research activity.

Therefore, the career trajectory of Spanish academics is shaped by four national accreditations and four institutional tests. Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the academic career path in Spain.

Figure 1. Academic career path in Spain.

Methodology

The main objective of this study is to analyze the academic identity of current university faculty using participatory visual methodologies. Although the study of identity has

traditionally taken a qualitative approach in which the interview has predominantly been used as a data collection technique, the visual approach opens up new possibilities for research and the production of knowledge in the study of identity, as it facilitates the expression and reflection of the participating subjects (Pain,2012).

Visual methodologies are based on a research approach involving the creation, analysis, or dissemination of images to study phenomena (Prosser,2014). Of the four visual methodological typologies described in the literature, this study employed the constructed imagery-as-data methodology (Shannon-Baker and Edwards, 2018). This consists of a two-phase process: 1) the creation or co-creation of the images by the participants, the researchers, both, or an external agent; and 2) reflection on the content of the images, either orally (interviews) or in writing (diaries). In the specific case of this study, the researchers generated the images from the descriptions and verifications of the research subjects; and the process of reflection was carried out verbally through dialogical and conversational processes.

In short, this form of data collection is fundamentally based on the interpretations, reflections, and meanings individuals give to their own experiences. Furthermore, the use of this methodology allows us to encourage reflection on themselves and their interactions with the environment, to reveal conscious and unconscious emotions, and to enrich the data collected by providing nuances and details (emotions, desires) that are difficult to capture through other traditional research methods (Shannon-Baker and Edwards,2018; Kortegast et al.,2019).

Information collection process and data analysis

The data collection process consisted of three distinct phases, which build upon each other as a cascading process of reflective deepening (Kelchtermans,2016). The first

phase consisted of in-depth interviews to analyze the professional trajectory, personal situation, climate of interpersonal relations in the work context, and the experiences and opinions of the subjects concerning different aspects such as the training received, the development of their functions, and the processes of access and promotion. The aim of this first phase was twofold. First, we wanted to become familiar with the background of the study participants to understand the reasons underlying the images created regarding their current situation at the university. Second, we wanted to generate a space of trust between the researcher and participants to facilitate future creation and reflection on the images. The interview culminated with a question asking participants to describe an image that captures their current viewpoint and feelings about their situation in the university.

Initially, the lead researcher proceeded to digitally create the images from the descriptions. Then, in a second session, the participants were shown the created images, and a dialogic process of improvement was generated based on the nuances added by the participants (e.g., color, size, shape, and position). The aim was to adjust the created image to the one imagined and described by the participants as accurately as possible. This co-creation process was used to avoid any effects of the participants' possible technical and creative limitations.

The third and last phase of reflexive deepening consisted of a final conversational interview in which participants were asked to describe their images and explain the reasoning behind them and the details contained in them. The purpose of this phase was to determine the meaning given to the images through the participants' voices.

We conducted both narrative and paradigmatic analyses on the information obtained. In the case of the narrative analysis, a vertical study of each case was carried out to deepen

understanding. Thus, the analysis focuses on the study participants individually and allows us to define the specific identity of each one. For the paradigmatic analysis, a horizontal study of the content was carried out, highlighting the participants' common themes, patterns, forms, and milestones. In both cases, thematic analysis was applied (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To facilitate these analyses, the qualitative software Nvivo 12 was used, which allows for an organized and structured coding of the text, images, sounds, and videos.

Participants

Key informants were selected through deliberate processes based on whether or not they met certain requirements and characteristics. For this, it is essential to determine with certainty that the chosen population includes the specific characteristics of the population profile to be analyzed (Flyvbjerg and Casado, 2006). In this sense, certain profiles (characteristics and attributes) were established that must be met by the interviewees, that is, of Social Sciences' academics (men and women) from different Andalusian public universities of all professional categories except full professor, as this is the last category and its progress is not subject to evaluation. The discipline of Social Sciences was selected because it is considered one of the most affected by scientific publication processes (shorter tradition in the scientific publishing world, fewer high impact journals, imbalance in favour of positivist research, etc.) (González-Calvo, 2020; Mula-Falcón and Caballero, 2023).

Following these characteristics, we employed two types of non-probabilistic sampling. First, convenience sampling was applied (Martínez-Salgado, 2012) to recruit volunteers who showed their interest in response to mass messages sent electronically. Second, non-probability snowball sampling was used (Noy, 2007), generating a final sample of

23 study participants reached after thematic saturation. However, the cases that were most clear, representative and showed the highest degree of interest and commitment in the visual methodology phase were selected for this study.

Table 1. Characteristics of the study participants.

	Age	Gender	Category
Participant 1	25	Male	Predoctoral fellow
Participant 2	33	Female	Assistant Doctor
Participant 3	36	Male	Assistant Doctor
Participant 4	31	Female	Substitute ¹
Participant 5	33	Male	Contracted Doctor
Participant 6	28	Female	Predoctoral fellow
Participant 7	37	Male	University Professor

Note: 1. Temporary contract aimed to cover special department necessities.

Ethical considerations

From the outset, this research received the approval of the ethics committee of the home university, as well as the participants' written and verbal informed consent. This consent included information such as the voluntary and anonymous nature of the research and the ability to withdraw or continue taking part in the research without any harm.

Furthermore, to guarantee anonymity, the participants' names were concealed, while any information that could facilitate their identification was omitted. Finally, all the information collected (interviews and images) was subjected to verification processes by the participants.

Results

For the description of the results, the images are presented together with short interview excerpts to achieve a better understanding of the images from the perspective of their creators (emic). Therefore, the voices of the participants themselves will be shown below.

Participant 1

"At the moment I feel like a puppet acting out of inertia with no voice and no vote. Even if at the beginning I had clear principles and ideas about how I wanted to be and act, my environment has gradually tied strings to me that mark my ways of thinking. Ways that respond to the rapid need to advance and remain at the university. Now my initial principles and convictions have been replaced (and forgotten) by the right ways to continue. And those ways are clear, and there are only two options: to accept them and try, or not to accept them and, quite possibly, to give up. So, faced with the fear of not being able to continue and satisfy my basic life needs, I find myself acting according to those rules of the game that I neither understand nor share, but on which my future depends. And I am disappointed in myself for having failed my own ideals. I dream of a day when I can break free, but at the same time fear that day will never come because I forget who I truly am and become just another puppet like the rest (*referring*

to the work environment)".

Participant 2

"I represent myself without a face, because I keep changing them. That's why I have faces around me, the faces I use depending on what I have to do, as if it were my wardrobe. But that need to keep changing faces and thinking about which one I'm going to choose generates a lot of anxiety and tiredness, like when you're choosing clothes to go on a date: will it match? will I be dressed up enough? will it fit me well? Moreover, those faces also speak, judge, and generate insecurity in me: are you going to wear that? do I think maybe I'll look better on you? And it's their voices that end up choosing for me, even if deep down I don't like it. So I feel like nobody. I do a thousand things and in none of them do I feel confident. I go from one to another, trying to respond to all of them, but in all of them I feel that I am not capable. And in order to try to fulfil this, I change my way of being by copying others who I know are successful, in an attempt to get ahead".

Participant 3

"For me, university is a continuous countdown (*referring to the next evaluation process*). A deadline that dictates everything I do and that generates pressure, stress, and anxiety. That is the reason for this image, because I feel like the sand (time) is falling little by little, filling everything around me with sand, until in the end I drown. Writing two articles, bureaucracy, tutoring a thesis, a meeting, directing a project... This constant clock ticking backwards means that I can't focus my attention and I can't dedicate all the time that things require, ending up with results that are far from desirable and making me feel unaccomplished and frustrated. And all of this is always due to the fear of running out of time. Moreover, this countdown isolates me, hence the idea of being locked in a clock. Never getting anywhere or always having to struggle to get to everything on time means that I gradually ignore and forget important things like family, friends, and myself. That's why I'm alone in the clock because that countdown has locked me in and isolated me".

Participant 4

"I had always been told that an academic career was a long-distance race. However, I had never been told that at the beginning it was an obstacle course with very obvious disadvantages that, no matter how hard you run, it's not up to you. And so it is, we all run to get into university, but it's not the best who get in, it's the best placed who get in. Some ride a motorized bike while others run; some, like me, have to pull 20kg weights (*referring to the fact that I am a mother and an academic*); we also have those who start 30 meters from the finish line and those who start 5 meters from the finish line. And all these factors depend only on luck, i.e., whether you landed on a good street or not (*referring to the working group*). But the fact is that despite the discouragement that this generates, the love for this profession leads you to try again and again. The problem is when, no matter how hard you run, no matter how hard you work, no matter who you overtake, you reach the end, and you realize that the trophy can only be reached in a certain street. That's when disappointment, frustration, and the desire to give it all up sets in. That's where I find myself".

Participant 5

"I imagine myself in a tunnel in search of hope, of my dream, of getting to where I want to be and being able to do what I want to do. Throughout my career, from the moment I started until now, it has been like walking towards the light, a light that would mean freedom, that is, to be able to do and devote myself to whatever I really want or feel like doing and not only to what I should. But I am already beginning to think that the light is nothing more than a mirage or, rather, that "carrot" from the fable of the donkey¹.

Because every time I seem to reach it, that is, every time I manage to reach a category that I thought would give me that freedom, the light changes its place. And I start to think that no matter how far I go, I won't reach it and I will always end up doing what I have to do and not what I want to do. So, I feel like that donkey in the fable, struggling all his life to reach a carrot that he will never reach."

¹ The fable of the donkey explains that to get a donkey to pull the cart, you have to put a carrot in front of him, close enough so that he thinks he can catch it, but just enough so that he can't reach it. In this way, the donkey is motivated to walk towards the carrot (which he will never reach) and do his job.

Participant 6

"My feeling is of walking towards a precipice. When you start with the illusion of stability you don't see the end, you just see how beautiful the views look, a beautiful landscape that you seem to be heading towards. However, as you move forward you realize that between you and the view there is a precipice, and that your current situation is nothing more than a "false stability" in which every step you take forward is a step towards the abyss (*referring to job insecurity and instability*). Every step, every victory (*referring to academic achievements*) is no longer satisfying as it was at the beginning; in that moment of the image, happiness is instantaneous because you know that, with every achievement, you take a step towards the fall. Moreover, it is a very uncertain precipice because you don't know what awaits you below (water, rocks, more abyss), nor how long you will be in freefall. At that moment everything becomes black and white, hell, it's not going to be black and white... if I'm walking towards the abyss, towards my "death ."And there, alone and about to turn 30, is when you start looking for anything, even if it's an old parachute, to do whatever you can to try to make the fall as minimal or as light as possible (*referring to practices such as publishing and exchanging authors' names, doing courses for a degree or ignoring the thesis in favor*

of increasing scientific production, among other aspects) because it's either that or god knows what".

Participant 7

"My image would be this because working in what we do requires balance. So, I think of myself as a tightrope walker who wants to get to the end of the rope without falling off. And because I do what I like and I'm quite good at it, I'm completely happy on that rope. There are many balances to manage and they change (*referring to work, professional relationships, personal life*). Also, as you go along, the rope gets thinner and thinner to challenge me, but I think it's appropriate because, otherwise, we relax. And it's also a good screening method. If you want to get there, you have to be the best tightrope walker, full stop. For that, sometimes you have to make sacrifices, like, for example, letting go of ballast. I understand that sometimes letting go of ballast can mean more or less depending on each person. But they are necessary sacrifices if you want to get there, if not... do something else: lion tamer, clown, juggler... "

Discussion and conclusions

This study aimed to *analyze the academic identity of today's university faculty*, exploring the factors that have an impact on this identity and the consequences that they

generate. To this end, a visual methodology was applied, i.e., an alternative research approach to the usual qualitative tradition in studying academic identity. The results offer an insight into the various identities that emerged from the feelings and self-perceptions of the participants. Furthermore, the findings allowed us to detect common patterns among the various identity positions. This section highlights the most relevant findings and discusses these in relation to other research results in the field.

From a broader perspective, our analysis of the seven cases has revealed the particular impact of various contextual factors on their respective identities. In each case, it has been possible to observe the varying degrees of emphasis on different elements contributing to the development of subtly different identities. It is important to bear in mind that, as we pointed out at the outset, academic identity is heterogeneous. Each individual possesses a unique identity, characterized by their distinct perspectives and approaches when faced with similar situations (Clarke et al.,2013; Kreber, 2010).

Thus, both Participants 1 and 5 must grapple with an internal identity conflict between their personal vision of academia and the stark realities they face. This internal debate generates a continuous self-negotiation process that provokes tensions (Shams,2019) and leads to the development of identities that, although different, share the values and ways of working within current academia. This finding is in accord with the study by Mula-Falcón et al. (2021), which concludes that submission to the new values and demands of today's universities has transformed academic identities over the past decade. This fact is explained by the need to access, promote, or obtain incentives within the profession (Clarke and Knights,2015; Cannizzo,2017; Djerasimovic and Villani,2019).

For instance, consider Participant 1, whose inner conflict centers on reconciling their initial vision of academia and the performative realities they must face. This internal debate ultimately leads to an acceptance of the demands of the university environment (particularly the heightened emphasis on scientific production) as a means of navigating the competitive university landscape. As the participant expresses, "*[...] faced with the fear of not being able to continue and satisfy my basic necessities of life, I find myself acting according to those rules of the game that I neither understand nor share, but on which my future depends*". According to Ylijoki and Ursin (2013) and Leisyte (2015), this identity is aptly labeled as "Lost", characterized by a surrender to the expectations of academic output. In this situation, prevailing negative feelings stem from the loss of one's core values or conceptions in the face of institutional demands.

Turning to Participant 5, a persistent internal conflict arises between their aspirations and the obligations imposed upon them: "*to be able to do and dedicate myself to whatever I want [...] and not only to what I should*". This internal struggle mirrors the findings of Saura and Bolívar (2019), culminating in acceptance and compliance with the demands of contemporary academia. However, in this instance, the driving force behind this transformation is not mere survival, but rather the quest to secure a more stable position that affords greater autonomy in fulfilling their professional responsibilities, as demonstrated by Acker and Webber (2017). This pursuit of freedom was expressed by the participant through the donkey metaphor and symbolized by the image of the light at the end of the tunnel.

In contrast, this internal debate is less pronounced in the remaining participants.

Nevertheless, we can observe the impact of other elements inherent to the contemporary university environment, such as job insecurity, the relentless pressure to meet evaluation

criteria, and the presence of inequalities surrounding access and promotion procedures in the Spanish academic system.

Participant 3 emphasizes the profound impact of the constant work overload stemming from the relentless pressure to pass the assessment processes. This excessive workload is predominantly focused on research-related tasks, as evidenced by the list of tasks to be carried out: *"writing two articles, bureaucracy, tutoring a thesis, a meeting, directing a project..."*. As a consequence, the participant cites the emergence of family and health issues, including stress and anxiety, which contribute to a sense of job dissatisfaction and frustration. Huang and Guo (2019) term this identity as a "stressed academic identity", which encapsulates elements such as a perceived inability to cope with demands (primarily due to time constraints), and the presence of negative emotions such as fear, anxiety, and exhaustion (Ursin et al., 2020).

In the case of Participant 4, the evaluation processes organized by the universities appear to be a decisive element in shaping their identity. Specifically, the competitiveness, as expressed through the athletic track metaphor, and the presence of inequalities, illustrated by describing the advantages and disadvantages of the contestants (going out first, riding a bike, carrying a weight). This situation, characterized by extreme competitiveness and the presence of inequalities is one of the most concerning aspects of the current Spanish university system (González-Calvo, 2020; Torraldo and Duque-Calvache, 2023). Much like Participant 4, this situation engenders feelings of disillusionment and frustration that could encourage individuals to leave the profession. According to Kalfa et al. (2018), this strategy is the most common among early-career academics.

Regarding Participant 6, job insecurity emerges as a prominent factor in shaping their academic identity. This situation of unpredictability and vulnerability has compelled them to resort to "unethical" practices or shift their focus away from their doctoral thesis to prioritize scientific output. This identity is referred to by Huang and Guo (2019) as that of an "expelled academic" characterized by coping with the demands of the situation through the use of unscrupulous and conventional tactics, driven by the fear of expulsion from academia. According to Saura and Bolívar (2019), the precarious nature of academic positions and job insecurity render academics more susceptible to the pressures exerted by the accountability-driven system.

In Participant 2's identity, a notable feature is the imitation of respected or successful peers, which plays a significant role in shaping their identity. The international literature suggests that this survival strategy can result in fragile identities that foster a sense of inauthenticity (Malauma et al., 2020). Furthermore, the presence of a strong sense of inadequacy and self-doubt in handling the demands of academic work is indicative of impostor syndrome, contributing to an underdeveloped sense of academic self (Reybold and Alamia, 2008). This aspect, as observed in the cases analyzed by Ursin et al. (2020), generates heightened levels of insecurity and anxiety.

Finally, Participant 7's identity is the only one distinguished by a positive outlook characterized by satisfaction with assessment systems. This identity aligns with the work of Ylijoki and Ursin (2013) and Leisyte (2015), which they refer to as "Success" or "Hybrid" Identity. It is common for individuals in certain disciplines to thrive within the academic evaluation system or to effectively navigate the demands of academia (Huang and Guo, 2019).

However, in the rest of the cases examined, a prevalent theme is high job dissatisfaction, coupled with negative emotions such as fear, disappointment, frustration, unfulfillment, exhaustion, and disillusionment, resulting in health issues that include stress, anxiety, and fatigue. These emotions are not only apparent in the interviews but also reflected in the depictions in the images, often characterized by the use of dark tones and emotionless expressions on the faces. These findings are consistent with other studies that have identified similar emotions and health issues among academics (Ursin et al.,2020). These feelings and the physical manifestations that are evident when carrying out professional activities contribute to the elevated rates of burnout experienced within the academic profession (Guthrie et al.,2017), a syndrome described by Han (2012) as “the epidemic of the 21st century”.

To conclude, our study highlights the significant influence of contextual factors, particularly the evaluation process, on the formation of academic identities among university faculty. Moreover, we have identified additional elements that amplify this impact, including job insecurity, the quest for access, job stability, and autonomy in carrying out their duties, as well as the presence of nepotism and competitiveness in access procedures. As a result, we have observed the emergence of diverse identities, each with different nuances, yet united by a common thread: a submission to the demands of evaluation processes, resulting in emotional repercussions such as fear, disappointment, frustration, and dissatisfaction, as well as adverse health consequences (e.g., stress, anxiety, and fatigue).

Policy and professional implications

In the current academic landscape, university faculty must develop their careers in a culture where securing permanent employment seems increasingly difficult, and where

their future depends largely on their ability to publish. Given these circumstances, it is essential to conduct a thorough re-evaluation of the framework that governs the current academic world, particularly focusing on evaluation systems characterized by an excessive quantification of research quality. Therefore, we must reflect on the type of university and academic environment we aspire to have and create criteria that are aligned with this vision. To do so, it is necessary to: 1) re-evaluate the concept of university quality; 2) reorient evaluations towards new, more qualitative standards of assessment; 3) develop criteria that encompass the full range of academic responsibilities; and 4) adapt criteria to suit the unique characteristics of each discipline, among other considerations.

Finally, improving working conditions and creating more opportunities are essential for enabling educators to excel in their roles (Djerasimovic and Villani, 2019). However, to effect meaningful change, it must be endogenous, i.e., it must be internally driven by the institutions and their stakeholders. Therefore, the dissenting voices that question and challenge the prevailing culture in academia must be made visible. We also advocate for fostering open dialogues that raise awareness of the current state of universities and the experiences of academic professionals. These dialogues can serve as a critical starting point from which to generate structural, organizational, and professional reforms, particularly by showing that behind the evaluations, there are professionals who yearn for a more fulfilling academic and social life. Such efforts will provide a platform for politicians, administrators, and decision-makers to recognize the realities and consider potential alternatives to the current academic culture.

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References

- Acker, S., & Webber, M.(2017).Made to measure: early career academics in the Canadian university workplace. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 36(3),541-554,<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2017.1288704>
- Alonso, I., Lobato, C. & Arandia, M.(2015). La identidad profesional docente como clave para el cambio en la educación superior. *Opción*,31(5),51-74.
- Apreile, K., Ellem, P., & Lole, L.(2020).Publish, perish, or pursue? Early career academics’ perspectives on demands for research productivity in regional universities. *Higher Education Research & Development*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2020.1804334>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V.(2006).Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2),77-

101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

Browning, L., Thompson, K., & Dawson, D.(2017).From early career researcher to research leader: survival of the fittest? *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 39(4),361-377.<https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2017.1330814>

Cannizzo, F.(2017).‘You’ve got to love what you do’: Academic labour in a culture of authenticity. *The Sociological Review*, 66(1),91-

106.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0038026116681439>

Clarke, C., & Knights, D.(2015).Careering through academia: Securing identities or engaging ethical subjectivities? *Humans relations*, 68(12),1865-1888.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726715570978>

Clarke, M., Hyde, A. & Drennan, J.(2013). Professional identity in Higher Education. In B. Kehn y U. Teichler (Eds.), *The academic profession in Europe: New tasks and new challenges* (pp.7-21). Springer.https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4614-5_2

Djerasimovic, S., & Villani, M.(2019).Constructing academic identity in the European higher education space: Experiences of early career educational researchers.

European Educational Research Journal, 1-

22.<https://doi.org/10.1177/1474904119867186>

Fernandez-Cano, A.(2021).Letter to the Editor: publish, publish ... cursed!.

Scientometrics,126,3673–3682.<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03833-7>

Flyvbjerg, B. & Casado, D.(2006).Cinco malentendidos acerca de la investigación mediante los estudios de caso. *RIES*,33(106).

- González-Calvo, G.(2020). El Agar.io Programado en la Enseñanza Superior: Fundamentos de la Dinámica del Superrendimiento y la Superproducción. *Qualitative Research in Education*,9(2),160-187.<https://doi.org/10.17583/qre.2020.5412>
- Guthrie, S. et al.(2017).*Understanding mental health in the research environment. A Rapid Evidence Assessment*. RAND Corporation.
- Han, B-Ch.(2012).*La sociedad del cansancio*. Herder.
- Huang, Y., & Guo, M.(2019).Facing disadvantages: The changing professional identities of college English teachers in a managerial context. *System*,82(1),1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.02.014>
- Javadi, Y., & Azizzadeh, S.(2020).Teacher’s Identity, Marketization of Higher Education, and Curriculum. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*,11(1),128-137. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1101.15>
- Jongbloed, B., Vossensteyn, H., Vught, F., & Westerheijden, F.(2018).Transparency in higher education: The emergence of a new perspective on higher education governance. In A. Curaj, L. Deca, & R. Pricopie (Eds.), *European higher education area: The impact of past and future policies* (pp.441–454). Springer.
- Kalfa, S., Wilkinson, A., & Gollan, P. J.(2018).The academic game: compliance and resistance in universities. *Work, Employment and Society*, 32(2), 274-291. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017017695043>
- Kelchtermans, G.(2016).The emotional dimension in teachers’ work lives: a narrative-biographical perspective. In M. Zembylas and P. Schutz (Eds.), *Methodological*

Advances in Research on Emotion and Education (pp.31-42).Springer.

Kie, D., & Harland, T.(2018).*Higher Education Research Methodology*. Routledge.

Kortegast, C., McCann, K., Branch, K., Latz, A., Turner, K., & Linder,

C.(2019).Enhancing ways of knowing: The case for utilizing participant-generated visual methods in higher education research. *Higher Education*,42(2),482-510.

<https://doi.org/10.1353/rhe.2019.0004><https://muse.jhu.edu/article/712605>

Kreber, C.(2010). Academics' teacher identities, authenticity and pedagogy. *Studies in Higher Education*, 35(2),171-194.<https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070902953048>

Lankveld, T., Schoonenboom, J., Volman, M., Croiset, G., & Beishuizen,

J.(2017).Developing a teacher identity in the university context: a systematic review of the literature. *Higher Education Research & Development*,36(2),325-342.<https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2016.1208154>

Leisyte, L.(2015).Changing academic identities in the context of a managerial university – bridging the duality between professions and organizations evidence from the U.S. and Europe. In W. Cummings & U. Teichler (Eds.), *The relevance of academic work in comparative perspective* (pp. 59-73). Springer.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11767-6_4

Macheridis, N., & Paulsson, N.(2021).Tracing accountability in higher education.

Research in education,110(1),78-97.<https://doi.org/10.1177/0034523721993143>

Malauma, I., Pick, D., & Htwe, H.(2020).‘Resistance and Compliance in Women’s

Academic Identity Work in the Global South’, *Higher Education Quarterly*,74,

257–72.

- Mantai, L.(2019).“Feeling more academic now”: Doctoral stories of becoming an academic. *The Australian Educational Researcher*,46(1),137-153.<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-018-0283-x>
- Martínez-Salgado, C.(2012).El muestreo en investigación cualitativa: principios básicos y algunas controversias. *Ciênc. saúde coletiva*,17(3).<https://doi.org/10.1590/S1413-81232012000300006>
- Mula-Falcón, J. & Caballero, K.(2022).Neoliberalism and its impact on academics: A qualitative review. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*,27(3),373-390.<https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2022.2076053>
- Mula-Falcón, J. & Caballero, K.(2023), Academics' perceptions regarding performance evaluations and the consequences for their professional and personal activity. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*.<https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-05-2023-0183>
- Mula-Falcón, J., Caballero, K., & Domingo, J.(2021).Exploring academics' identities in today's universities: A systematic review. *Quality Assurance in Education*,30(1),118-134.<https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-09-2021-0152>
- Noy, C.(2008).Sampling Knowledge: The Hermeneutics of Snowball Sampling in Qualitative Research. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*,11(4),327-344.<https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570701401305>
- Pain, H.(2012).A literature review to evaluate the choice and use of visual methods. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*,11(4),303–319.

- Prosser, J.(2014).Visual methodology: Towards a more seeing research. In N. Denzin & Y. Lincoln (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (pp.177–212). Thousand Oaks, CA:SAGE.
- Reybold, L., & Alemani, J.(2008).‘Academic transitions in education: A developmental perspective of women faculty experiences’, *Journal of Career Development*,35,107–128.
- Saura, G., & Bolívar, A.(2019).Sujeto académico neoliberal: Cuantificado, digitalizado y bibliometrificado. *REICE. Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*,17(4),9-26.<http://dx.doi.org/10.15366/reice2019.17.4.001>
- Shams, F.(2019).Managing academic identity tensions in a Canadian public university: the role of identity work in coping with managerialism. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*,41(6),619-132.<https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2019.1643960>
- Shannon-Baker, P. & Edwards, C.(2015).The Affordances and Challenges to Incorporating Visual Methods in Mixed Methods Research. *American Behavioral Scientist*,62(7),34-53.<https://doi.org.10.1177/0002764218772671>
- Sutton-Brown, C.(2014).Photovoice: A methodological guide. *Photography & Culture*, 7, 169–186.
- Torrado, J. & Duque-Calvache, R.(2023).Universidad y precariedad. Orígenes y consecuencias del modelo laboral de las universidades públicas españolas del siglo XXI. *Educación XXI*,26(1),47-69.<https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.33510>
- Ursin, J., Vähäsantanen, K., McAlpine L., & Hökkä, P.(2020).Emotionally loaded

identity and agency in Finnish academic work. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 44(3), 311-325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2018.1541971>

Ylijoki, O., & Ursin, J.(2013).The construction of academic identity in the changes of Finnish higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 38(8), 1135-1149. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2013.833036>

Zabalza, M.(2009). Ser profesor universitario hoy. *La Cuestión Universitaria*, 5(1), 68-80.